

Respective figure folder contain the raw data for that particular figure as well as the code for analyzing and plotting the data.

Software needed for processing Buridan raw data has been published before and is not included in this depository (Colomb et al. 2012). The software for tracking the fly as well as the evaluation algorithms can be found in a complete package at the following link <http://buridan.sourceforge.net/>.

In respective folder you will also find the figure files in png and ai format.

Colomb, Julien, Lutz Reiter, Jędrzej Błaszczewicz, Jan Wessnitzer, and Bjoern Brembs. 2012. "Open Source Tracking and Analysis of Adult *Drosophila* Locomotion in Buridan's Paradigm with and without Visual Targets." *PloS One* 7 (8): e42247.